

Field Data Collection Checklist (CHIGURU Cohort)

1. Household & Demographic Information

- Confirm household ID and participant ID are written correctly
- Record age (in years)
- Record marital status
- Record tribe/sub-tribe
- Record blood relationship with husband (if applicable)

2. Pregnancy and Reproductive History

- Record gravida (number of pregnancies)
- Record parity (number of live births)
- Record number of abortions and stillbirths
- Record number of live births
- Note any complications during delivery

3. Anthropometry

- Calibrate weighing scale with 10 kg weight before measurement
- Measure weight twice, note both, and calculate mean
- Measure height twice, note both, and calculate mean
- Calculate BMI using mean height and weight
- Record any visible health concerns (e.g., undernutrition signs)

4. Biological Sample Collection (Blood Tests)

- Label sample tube with participant ID before collection
- Collect 3–5 mL venous blood using standard sterile procedure
- Store samples at correct temperature (ice box in field, -80°C in lab)
- Transport samples to lab (VGKK → biorepository)
- Record haemoglobin, RBC count, MCV, sTfR, and ferritin after lab analysis

5. Dietary Diversity (HDDS / Food Frequency)

- Ask about 24-hr recall for each food group
- Tick if consumed: cereals, roots/tubers, vegetables, fruits, legumes/nuts, dairy, meat, eggs, fish, oils/fats
- Calculate Household Dietary Diversity Score (HDDS)
- Cross-check unusual values (very low or very high diversity)

6. Socioeconomic & Household Variables

- Record household size
- Record source of drinking water
- Record sanitation facility availability
- Record electricity and cooking fuel type
- Record participant occupation and education
- Record household Social Living Index (SLI) score

Signature/Initials of Enumerator: _____

Date of Data Collection: ___ / ___ / 20__